

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PRE-, WHILE-, AND POST-LISTENING ACTIVITIES IN ENHANCING LISTENING COMPREHENSION

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of pre-, while-, and post-listening activities on improving listening comprehension in ESL/EFL classrooms. Grounded in research and pedagogical theories, it highlights creative techniques and strategies for each stage of listening instruction. These stages help engage learners, scaffold comprehension, and consolidate understanding, making listening tasks more effective. Our analysis integrates insights from various scholarly works, emphasizing the necessity of structured listening activities and their implications for both students and educators. Practical recommendations are provided for implementing these stages in language instruction.

Keywords: Listening comprehension, ESL/EFL classrooms, Pre-listening activities, While-listening strategies, Post-listening activities.

Introduction

Listening is a foundational skill in language acquisition, yet it is often undervalued in ESL/EFL classrooms (Jones, 2008). Effective listening not only fosters comprehension but also supports learners in developing other language skills like speaking and vocabulary acquisition (Brown & Lee, 2015). Pre-, while-, and post-listening activities are essential in creating a structured approach to teaching listening. These stages ensure students are adequately prepared, engaged during the task, and reflective afterward (Houston, 2016).

The aim of this study is to explore the role of these stages in listening instruction and propose practical strategies for implementing them effectively. By synthesizing insights from previous studies, this research contributes to a better understanding of how structured activities can enhance listening skills.

Methods

This study relies on a review of existing literature, including research articles, pedagogical frameworks, and case studies on listening instruction. Works by Babenko (2016), Field (1997), and Kumar (2021) provide a theoretical basis for understanding the stages of listening. Additionally, practical approaches are drawn from Houston (2016) and Liao (2012), focusing on pre-listening preparation, active engagement during while-listening, and reflective exercises in post-listening.

My own perspective is incorporated into the analysis, particularly in tailoring these strategies to diverse classroom contexts, including technology integration as highlighted by Maulina et al. (2022).

Results and Discussion

Pre-Listening Activities

Pre-listening activities activate background knowledge and set the stage for comprehension (Khan, 2021).¹ Strategies include brainstorming, predicting, and discussing key vocabulary. These techniques create a schema, allowing learners to anticipate the content of the listening task (Brown & Lee, 2015).² For example, a short discussion on the topic of a podcast primes students for active engagement.

The importance of connecting pre-listening tasks to learners' interests. For instance, introducing culturally relevant topics can increase motivation and attention, especially in diverse classrooms.

While-Listening Activities

During this stage, learners process the audio input and engage in focused tasks such as note-taking, filling in gaps, or answering comprehension questions. Houston (2016) emphasizes dividing listening tasks into manageable chunks to reduce cognitive overload.

Using guided questions or visual aids during while-listening helps students stay focused. Additionally, providing transcripts for complex listening materials can serve as a supportive tool for lower-proficiency learners.

Post-Listening Activities

Post-listening tasks allow learners to consolidate understanding and reflect on their performance (Morley, 1991). Activities such as summarizing, discussing, or creating related projects are effective for reinforcing comprehension. According to Kumar (2021), feedback during this stage is crucial for addressing gaps in understanding.

Integrating technology-based tools, such as collaborative online platforms, can make post-listening activities more interactive. For example, students could use discussion boards or video presentations to share their reflections on the listening material.

Conclusion

Pre-, while-, and post-listening activities are indispensable for effective listening instruction in ESL/EFL contexts. These stages provide a structured framework that enhances engagement, comprehension, and retention. Our analysis underscores the importance of adapting these strategies to the needs of diverse learners and integrating innovative tools to enrich the learning experience.

Future research should explore the long-term effects of structured listening activities on language acquisition and investigate how these techniques can be customized for different age groups and proficiency levels.

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